

ANALYSIS OF THE INFLUENCE OF BEAN SEED INOCULATION WITH RHIZOBIUM PHASEOLUS BACTERIA ON BEAN MORPHOLOGICAL AND CHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS

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*SUMMARY: Experiment was carried out on the control surface of 1000 m² without bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris*) seed inoculation and on the experimental surface of 1000 m² with seed inoculated with bacteria *Rhizobium leguminosarum* bv. *phaseoli*. Common technology of bean cultivation was used, with absolutely identical interventions and circumstances, the only difference being the use of inoculated seed in the experimental cluster. This paper elaborates influences of inoculation on morphological properties (plant height, length of pod, size of bean) and chemical characteristics (proteins, raw fibres, ash, fats and humidity). Average values of the plant height in inoculated seed, size of the pod and average bean size are higher than in the control and this difference is statistically highly significant. Moreover, chemical analysis of bean (seed) showed 13,42% higher contents of proteins in inoculated seed, 5,68% higher ash contents, 10,34% higher fat contents, 1,26% higher celluloses contents and 8,68% higher humidity.*

Key words: *bean, seed inoculation, Phaseolus vulgaris, Rhizobium leguminosarum* bv. *phaseoli*.

INTRODUCTION

Bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris*) is annual herbaceous plant from the *Fabaceae* family, genus *Phaseolus*. There are five phases of bean development: phase one involves swelling and germination of the seed and plant springing, the second phase is the phase of vegetational mass or leaves, the third phase is blooming, the fourth phase is pod develop-

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ment and the fifth phase is full ripeness. Bean is a plant that requires a lot of warmth and humidity. It is cultivated in crop rotation and is good pre-crop for many agricultural and vegetable cultures. Bean on heavy, very acidic or extremely alkaline soils vegetates less effectively. Most suitable soils for bean are those with pH between 6,5 and 7,5 (Vasić et al., 2007). Among others, pH is a limiting factor in yield and quality of Leguminosae as well as the most of agricultural cultures (Tanaka et al., 1984). Nutritional value of bean is not contained only in its high contents of proteins (23 to 30%), but in its total contents of the most important amino acids (tyrosine, tryptophan, lysine, arginine, histidine, cysteine, methionine). Chemical characteristics are presented through the contents of proteins, celluloses, ash, fats and humidity. Morphological characteristics are the most important properties like: plant height, pod length, bean size and yield (Todorović et al., 2003). Bean belongs to legume family and has great agro technical significance because it leaves soil in very good physical and biological state, therefore it is an excellent pre-crop for many agricultural and vegetable cultures (Vidović and Todorović, 1988). It makes symbiosis with certain microorganisms of *Rhizobium* genus that have the ability of nitrogen fixation, that is the use of nitrogen from air. Bacteria from *Rhizobium leguminosarum* *bv. phaseoli*. are symbiotic gram-negative microorganisms of the soil that influence formation of root nodules. The efficiency of nitrogen fixation of nodular bacteria depends on bacteria specificity to live in symbiosis with only one type of plants (bean, pea, soy, clover), virulence – bacteria's ability to penetrate the root and reproduce, and activity – bacteria's ability to fix gaseous nitrogen from air in nodules. According to various sources, nitrogen quantity that remains in soil after bean sowing is some 3-170 kg/ha (average is 50 kg/ha). During a year, depending on ecological circumstances, Leguminosae in symbiosis with *Rhizobium* fix up to 400 kg N/ha (Veladžić et al., 2003). Bean's nodular bacteria exist even in our soils, but not in optimal numbers nor the most efficient strains. In the inoculum, there are selected strains that fixate gaseous nitrogen in the most intensive way and leave the greatest quantities of nitrogen in soil after bean plucking (Marinković, 2006; Milošević and Marinković, 2009). Rhizobia stimulate plant growth and development producing biologically active matters (vitamins, gibberellins and auxins) too (Alami et al., 2000; Egamberdiyeva, 2007). Nodule bacteria beans in our soils are in small numbers, particularly relating to land with an acid reaction (Burdman et al., 1996). Entering effective and acidoresistant strains of these bacteria during sowing beans, increases nitrogen fixation and allows the cultivation of these plant species in less fertile soils. (Milutinovic et al. 1992). In acidic, poorly humic soils, nitrogen fertilizers do not inhibit symbiotic nitrogen fixators because the land does not have enough affordable or nutrients for microorganisms or plant. The amount of nitrogen fixed varies depending on the effectiveness of nodule bacteria, which enter the composition of microbial fertilizers, and also the genotype of the plant. (Milic et al. 2004).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The experiment was set up in 2009 in two parcels; each was made of 1000m², in Bihac municipality, Bosnia and Herzegovina. The first parcel used as a control and we used bean seed *Phaseolus vulgaris* that was not inoculated. On the other parcel of the same size, seed inoculated with bacteria *Rhizobium leguminosarum* *bv. phaseoli* was used. On the experimental parcel, microbiological fertilizer with selected strains

of nodular bacteria was used and applied to bean seed just prior to seeding. Inoculum application was done in shade. It was applied to watered seed, in a ratio of 10g of inoculum per 1kg of seed (Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops, Novi Sad, nitragin). The seed was planted immediately after inoculation with bacterial preparation. Ploughing was done with ploughs reaching depth of 30cm. Fertilization was made with well rotted sheep manure in a quantity of 1500 kg per 1000m² on both parcels. Seeding was done on 02.05. 2009 in beds 8 to 10 cm apart with a distance of 50 cm between rows. For fertilization before sowing was used was 2 kg of NPK fertilizer (12:12:12), was used for supplemental feeding around 0.10 gr kristalon (pure nitrogen fertilizer) to 1.5 liters of water.

Seeds were planted at a depth of 4 to 5 cm. During germination and due to occurrence of soil crust, hoeing up was undertaken. The first inter-row hoeing up was undertaken when first “troper” leaves were formed, the second and the third cultivation was undertaken in span of 12 to 16 days. Sixty samples of bean were taken for this experiment. Thirty of them from inoculated parcel and thirty from control one. For every taken bean sample plant height, length of pod and length of bean were measured. Apart from that, all pods were ingathered aside from each parcel and on the basis of their weighing, yield per hectare was calculated. Moreover, the qualitative features of bean seeds were identified (proteins, lipids, humidity, ash and cellulose). Identification of these qualitative features of bean seed was performed in laboratories of Agricultural Institute of Una-Sana Canton. Analyses of proteins, lipids, humidity and ash were done after the manual Instrumental Methods in Biological Control (Veladžić and Čaklovića 2001).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Individual data were processed by the utilisation of mathematical-statistical methods. Analysis of statistical-variational parameters of plant height, pod length and bean size for control and inoculated parcel was done (Table 1).

Table 1. The statistical variations of the parameters stem, pods and bean cultivation methods for both beans

Tabela 1. Statističko varijacioni parametri za stabljiku, mahunu i zrno graha za oba načina uzgoja graha

Parcels / Parcele	X	SD	CV	Sx
Plant height (cm) / Visina stabljike (cm)				
Control / Kontrola	46,43	2,27	0,18	0,41
Inoculated / Inokulacija	52,35	6,13	0,18	1,12
Pod length (cm) / Veličina mahune (cm)				
Control / Kontrola	10,14	1,32	0,18	0,24
Inoculated / Inokulacija	12,19	1,88	0,18	0,34
Size of beans (cm) / Veličina zrna (cm)				
Control / Kontrola	1,15	0,20	0,19	0,04
Inoculated / Inokulacija	1,35	0,21	0,2	0,04

Where: **X** – mean, **SD** – standard deviation, **Cv** – coefficient of variation, **Sx** – error estimation
 Gde je: **X**-sr.vrednost, **SD**-standardna devijacija, **Cv**-koeficijent varijacije, **Sx**-ocena greške

Plant height: There is increase in plant height in inoculated bean seed for 12.75% in relation to control. Calculated values of indicator t_{12r} is 4.97 and is evidently larger than tabular value whose significance level is 0.1%. On that basis, it can be concluded that differences between arithmetic means of two samples are *very highly significant* and the null-hypothesis is rejected, $t_{calc} = 4.97***$.

Pod length: Average pod length in inoculated bean is for 20.22% larger than pods from control parcel. Calculated value of indicator $t_{calc} = 4.88$ and is also larger than tabular value of 0.1% significance level. On that basis, it can be concluded that differences between arithmetic means of two samples are *very highly significant* and the null-hypothesis is rejected, $t_{calc} = 4.88***$.

Size of beans: Average size of beans on inoculated parcel is for 17.39% larger than on control parcel. Calculated value of indicator $t_{calc} = 3.33$ and is also larger than tabular value of 0.1% significance level. On that basis, it can be concluded that differences between arithmetic means of two samples are *highly significant* and the null-hypothesis is rejected, $t_{calc} = 3.33**$.

Yield calculation on the observed parcels of 1000m² (inoculated seed and control-not inoculated) gave the following results: Yield of inoculated bean is 98 kg, i.e. 980 kg/ha. Yield of control bean is 80 kg, i.e. 800 kg/ha. Yield on parcel with inoculated bean seed in comparison to control parcel is noticeably increased for 180 kg, i.e. for 22.5%.

If it is kept in mind that the effect of bean inoculation caused the increase of yield in the amount of 180 kg, and if that amount is multiplied with market price of bean, which is 2€ currently, it means that the effect of financial increase is 360€. Apart from yield increase, it is very important that the soil is deposited with important supply of nitrogen (Marinković, 2006). The story does not end with only these effects. It is rather important to give the values of deposited nitrogen in soil after bean yield.

Table 2. Qualitative properties of beans (protein, fat, moisture, ash, and cellulose)
 Tabela 2. Kvalitativna svojstva zrna graha (belančevine, masti, vlaga, pepeo i celuloza)

Chemical characteristics <i>Hemijska svojstva</i>	Inoculated <i>Inokulisano</i>	Control <i>Kontrola</i>	Increase (%) <i>Povećanje (%)</i>
Proteins (%) <i>Belančevine (%)</i>	28.32	24.97	13.42
Ash (%) <i>Pepeo (%)</i>	4.84	4.58	5.68
Lipids (%) <i>Masti (%)</i>	1.28	1.16	10.34
Cellulose (%) <i>Celuloza (%)</i>	5.64	5.57	1.26
Humidity (%) <i>Vlaga (%)</i>	13.40	12.33	8.68

On the basis of identified results, it is noted that there is increase in chemical characteristics of inoculated bean, that is the content of proteins and lipids increased for over 10%, ash for 5.68%, cellulose for 1.26% and humidity for 8.68% (Table 2). These data about increased contents of proteins, lipids, ash, cellulose and water are in full accordance with many researchers' findings that inoculation of Leguminosae just prior to sowing produces positive effects on number of nodules, increases growth and yield, savings on nitrogen mineral fertilizers, increases quality of beans and biological

activity of the soil (Milošević and Marinković 2009; Yazdani et al., 2009; Gholami et al., 2009; Zaidi et al., 2006).

CONCLUSIONS

Regarding quantitative characteristics, there are statistically highly significant differences between inoculated and not inoculated beans regarding the increase of plant height, pod length and size of beans.

Yield analysis of inoculated bean showed yield of 980 kg/ha, and in control production yield of 800 kg/ha.

Regarding qualitative characteristics, positive effects on increase of contents of proteins 13.42%, ash 5.68%, lipids 10.34%, cellulose 1.26% and humidity 8.68% are identified.

Bean seed bacterisation with *Rhizobium leguminosarum* bv. *phaseoli*. prior to seeding should be considered obligatory and effective measure in bean production technology. It is particularly important on soils where bean has not been cultivated for longer period or at all.

The importance of bean inoculation is visible from decreased use of expensive nitrogen fertilizers, contribution to the improvement of soil quality, decreased burden of nitrogen mineral fertilizers on eco system and increased yield and quality of beans.

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ANALIZA UTJECAJA INOKULACIJE SEMENA GRAHA BAKTERIJAMA *RHIZOBIUM LEGUMINOSARUM BV. PHASEOLI*. NA MORFOLOŠKE I HEMIJSKE KARAKTERISTIKE GRAHA

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Izvod

Eksperiment je proveden na površini od 1000 m² bez inokulacije semena graha *Phaseolus vulgaris* (kontrolna) i na površini od 1000 m² gdje je korišteno inokulisano seme bakterijama (eksperimentalna) *Rhizobium leguminosarum bv. phaseoli*. U tehnologiji uzgoja graha korištena je uobičajna praksa, sa potpuno identičnim zahvatima i okolnostima, uz jedinu razliku što je u eksperimentalnoj skupini izvršena inokulacija semena. U radu su obrađeni utjecaji inokulacije semena na morfološke karakteristike (visina stabljike, dužina mahune, veličina zrna) i na hemijske (belančevine, sirova vlakna, pepeo, masti i vlagu). Srednje vrednosti visine stabljike kod inokulisanog semena, veličina mahune i prosečna veličina zrna su veće od kontrole i ta razlika

je visoko statistički značajna. Također je hemijskom analizom zrna (semena) utvrđen veći sadržaj belančevina kod inokulisanog semena za 13,42%, sadržaj pepela za 5,68%, sadržaj masti za 10,34%, sadržaj celuloze za 1,26% i sadržaj vlage za 8,68%.

Ključne reči: grah, inokulacija semena, *Phaseolus vulgaris*, *Rhizobium leguminosarum* bv. *phaseoli*.

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